

Multicomponent anion exchange simulation of phosphate removal and recovery from municipal wastewater using Aspen Adsorption

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ABSTRACT

Phosphorus (P) is a finite resource. The depletion of P resources is expected to be reached within a few hundred years. P recovery from municipal wastewater is essential for mitigating eutrophication and ensuring sustainable resource use. Adsorption and ion exchange (IEX) represent promising alternatives to conventional removal methods, offering selective recovery and compliance with increasingly stringent discharge limits. This study presents the first application of Aspen Adsorption to simulate multicomponent continuous-flow P removal and recovery from actual wastewater. The tested sorbent is pyroaurite, a Fe-rich hydrotalcite with high phosphate selectivity. Experimental breakthrough and regeneration tests were reproduced through an Aspen-based multicomponent ion exchange model incorporating competition from chloride, sulphate, and bicarbonate. A hybrid parameter estimation procedure enabled robust calibration of equilibrium constants and mass transfer coefficients, overcoming convergence challenges. The validated model successfully predicted (i) the scale-up from 20 to 60 cm packed beds, (ii) repeated adsorption/desorption cycles through the Cycle Organizer, and (iii) the impact of salinity increases relevant to coastal wastewater scenarios. Results showed high correlation between simulations and experimental data ($R^2 \geq 0.90$) and demonstrated that pyroaurite maintained effective P removal under saline conditions, with only moderate efficiency losses. These findings highlight Aspen Adsorption as a powerful tool for the design, optimization, and scale-up of phosphate recovery processes, contributing to bridge the gap between lab-scale testing and full-scale application.

1. Introduction

The increasing concern over environmental sustainability and resource recovery leads to significant interest in nutrient recovery from wastewater. Phosphorus, an essential nutrient, is commonly found in municipal wastewater in the form of phosphates. Its recovery is crucial not only for preventing eutrophication in aquatic systems but also for its reuse as a valuable resource in agriculture and industry [1]. Phosphorus is a finite resource. At the current rate of fossil P mining ($30 \cdot 10^6 \text{ tP y}^{-1}$), depletion of P resources is expected to be reached within a few hundred years [2]. Thus, P was listed as a critical raw material by the European Union [3].

P removal from municipal wastewater (MWW), which is crucial to protect water bodies from eutrophication, offers a promising opportunity for phosphorus recovery [4]. Thus, the revised Wastewater Treatment Directive 2024/3019 reduced the limit for wastewater treatment

plant (WWTP) discharges to $0.5\text{--}0.7 \text{ mgP L}^{-1}$ depending on the WWTP size, and delegated the European Commission to set a minimum rate of P recovery from MWW or sludge.

P is traditionally removed from wastewater through chemical precipitation or enhanced biological removal. Both methods transfer P to sludge, where it can be recovered through struvite precipitation or by extracting it from incinerated ash [5]. A promising alternative is represented by adsorption and ion exchange (IEX), which offer several advantages: i) a final product suitable for fertilizer production is obtained; ii) no additional sludge is generated; iii) a greater control over effluent quality is possible, helping to meet new, stricter wastewater discharge limits [1] [6]. Several adsorbents and anion exchangers proved efficient and selective for phosphate removal from MWW: biochar, hydrotalcites, Fe-doped anion exchange resins, metal oxides [7–12] [13,14] [15]. A large number of phosphate adsorption/IEX studies consisted of batch tests, or continuous-flow tests conducted with

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synthetic solutions [16], whereas a limited number of studies focused on phosphate continuous-flow adsorption/IEX from actual MWW [1] [6] [17] [18].

The simulation of continuous-flow processes of P adsorption/IEX from MWW, including mass transfer limitations and anion competition and calibrated on a wide set of continuous-flow experimental data, represents a crucial tool for process optimization and scale-up. In particular, P adsorption simulation can effectively integrate and expand the information provided by experimental studies, thanks to the possibility to i) assess the effect of variations in operational conditions, such as the concentration of competing anions or the contact time; ii) assess the process performances during a high number of repeated adsorption/desorption cycles, which would require an extremely time-consuming experimental work; and iii) evaluate the adsorption performances at the packed bed heights and diameters typical of real-world applications, and thus perform the preliminary design of a full-scale process. However, the literature analysis indicates a lack of studies focusing on the complete simulation of dynamic P adsorption/IEX. Indeed, among the studies that include the dynamic simulation of phosphate adsorption/IEX, the vast majority used simplified adsorption models, such as the Thomas or Adams-Bohart model, that do not take into account mass-transfer resistance, axial dispersion or competition by other anions [15] [19] [20] [21]. Only a few studies applied more comprehensive simulation models, based on the advection/dispersion equation and capable of taking into account mass-transfer resistances [22]. However, to the best of the authors' knowledge, all the studies that modelled P adsorption/IEX from MWW only considered P, neglecting the competitive effect exerted by other anions. Expanding the analysis beyond P recovery from MWW, an extremely limited number of studies included the simulation of multicomponent anion exchange [23] [24].

Aspen Adsorption represents a powerful tool to simulate multicomponent adsorption/IEX, thanks to the possibility to: i) calibrate the model on experimental data; ii) simulate adsorption/regeneration cycles through the Cycle Organizer; iii) take into account competition between different compounds; and iv) integrate the process with other Aspen functions, such as the inclusion of other plant components and the cost analysis. The use of Aspen Adsorption to simulate multicomponent gas-phase adsorption processes has been reported in several studies [25] [26] [27] [28]. In the field of liquid-phase adsorption processes, Aspen Adsorption has been implemented mainly to simulate heavy metal separation from various water streams [29] [30] [31] [32] [33] [34] [35], whereas few studies addressed anion removal [36] [37]. The analysis of the liquid-phase Aspen-based adsorption studies highlights major research gaps: i) no study included the simulation of desorption, or the use of the model to scale-up experimental data to full scale; ii) in most cases, the simulations are not based on experimental data obtained with actual wastewater; iii) the simulation of multicomponent liquid-phase adsorption/IEX – which presents specific convergence challenges due to the high number of parameters to be estimated – was considered by only two previous studies, which did not include a rigorous model calibration on experimental data [31] [33]; iv) most papers do not report all the parameters used in the simulations or do not justify the values adopted.

The main goal of this study is to address the above-listed research gaps, through the development of the Aspen Adsorption-based multicomponent simulation of a wide set of continuous flow tests of P adsorption & desorption from actual MWW. The experimental tests, described by Maggetti et al. [15], were conducted in columns packed with 20 to 60 cm of pyroaurite, an innovative Fe-containing layered double hydroxide developed in-house at the University of Bologna. Pyroaurite was selected for this simulation study among other potential sorbents for multiple reasons: it features high P sorption capacities (20 mg_P g⁻¹ in batch, 12 mg_P g⁻¹ in continuous-flow tests, at 7 mg_P L⁻¹ with actual WWTP effluent); it has a very high selectivity towards phosphate; it can be effectively regenerated and re-used over numerous adsorption/desorption cycles at constant adsorption performances [15]. P

adsorption on Fe-based layered double hydroxides (LDH) can be ascribed to three mechanisms: i) electrostatic adsorption: the LDH positively charged surface and the abundant hydroxyl groups promote P uptake via electrostatic attraction and surface complexation with negatively charged phosphate species; ii) interlayer anions (e.g., chloride and bicarbonate) can be exchanged with phosphate through ion-exchange processes; iii) ligand complexation: phosphate can directly interact with the metal layers, forming stable inner-sphere complexes, including M–P–M bridging structures [38].

The specific goals of the present study are:

- i) quantifying the entity of anion competition in the process of continuous-flow phosphate adsorption/IEX from MWW, by means of a multicomponent simulation conducted with Aspen Adsorption;
- ii) testing the capacity of Aspen Adsorption to predict the effect of a bed height scale-up from 20 to 60 cm at constant EBCT, using literature correlations to estimate the variation in mass-transfer coefficient with superficial velocity;
- iii) demonstrating the capacity of the Aspen Adsorption Cycle Organizer to predict the column behaviour during repeated adsorption/desorption cycles;
- iv) predicting the effect on the P removal/recovery performances of using a saline MWW, an increasingly frequent situation in coastal regions as a result of climate change.

Each of these goals represents a specific novelty of this work, since none of the above-listed Aspen Adsorption features has been previously investigated in the literature relative to liquid-phase adsorption processes.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Characteristics of the tested municipal wastewater

The continuous flow tests of P adsorption and recovery simulated in this work were conducted using an actual effluent of a municipal wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) located in Northern Italy, whose composition is reported in Table 1. The P concentration of the WWTP effluent was slightly below 1.0 mg_P L⁻¹, as required by the EU Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive 91/271. Thus, the treated WW was spiked with a KH₂PO₄:K₂HPO₄ solution (2:1 w/w) to raise the P concentration to 7 ± 0.5 mg_P L⁻¹, the typical value in a municipal WWTP effluent if no P removal is implemented [39].

Table 1
Main characteristics of the tested WWTP effluent.

Compound	Average value ±95% conf. Interval (mg L ⁻¹)
BOD ₅	15 ± 2
COD	29 ± 2
Total susp. Solids	5.3 ± 0.6
Phosphate (as P) ^a	1.0 ± 0.2
Chloride	150 ± 12
Nitrate (as N)	1.5 ± 0.5
Sulphate	104 ± 9
Bicarbonate	615 ± 58
Ammonium	3.9 ± 0.3
Sodium	101 ± 8
Potassium	13 ± 2
Magnesium	14 ± 1
Calcium	83 ± 6
pH ^b	7.9 ± 0.2

^a Spiked to 7 ± 0.5 mg_P L⁻¹.

^b pH units.

2.2. Sorbent characteristics, isotherms and kinetic tests

The sorbent used in this paper for P adsorption/IEX from MWW is pyroaurite, a Fe-rich hydroxalite ($\text{Mg}_6\text{Fe}_2(\text{OH})_{16}[\text{CO}_3] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$), synthesized at the University of Bologna according to the procedure described previously [15]. The solid obtained from the synthesis was calcined to increase its surface area, then crushed and sieved to the 0.355–0.710 mm particle size range. This procedure resulted in an $80 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}_{\text{dry}}^{-1}$ surface area and a $620 \text{ g L}_{\text{bed volume}}^{-1}$ bulk density. Pyroaurite was initially tested by means of isotherm tests conducted as illustrated previously [15]. It was further characterized by means of a kinetic test conducted as illustrated in Text S1, Supplementary Material.

2.3. Continuous-flow tests operational conditions

Pyroaurite was initially packed in a 30-cm column packed with 20 cm of resin bed, which was used to conduct 4 consecutive P adsorption/IEX breakthrough (BT) tests. Since pyroaurite is an innovative sorbent produced in-house, the 20-cm packed bed was selected as a compromise between the needs to minimize the amount of sorbent to be produced and attain an acceptable fluid-dynamic behaviour. The 20-cm bed resulted in a satisfactory packing quality [15]. Based on the satisfactory results obtained in the 20-cm bed, further pyroaurite was produced, and the process was scaled up in a 90-cm column packed with 60 cm of resin bed, the minimum height used in industrial applications. Preliminary fluid-dynamic tests conducted with a NaOH 2% w/w tracer solution were used to estimate the total effective porosity (63%) and the longitudinal dispersivity (0.030 m), following the experimental and data elaboration approach illustrated previously [15,34,40]. The Anion Exchange Capacity (AEC) was determined by desorbing and analyzing P from a sorbent bed previously saturated with a 1 N $\text{KH}_2\text{PO}_4\text{:K}_2\text{HPO}_4$ solution (2:1 w/w) as previously illustrated [17]. AEC resulted equal to $119 \text{ mg}_P \text{ g}_{\text{dry}}^{-1}$ sorbent, corresponding to $4770 \text{ eq. m}_{\text{dry}}^{-3}$ sorbent.

Four consecutive P adsorption/IEX breakthrough (BT) tests were conducted in the 20-cm pyroaurite packed bed, and a 5th test was operated in the 60-cm packed bed. All BT tests were conducted at a 5 min empty bed contact time (EBCT). Temperature was controlled at $23 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ by flowing water in the column jacket. Adsorption performance was quantified in selected breakthrough tests as the number of MWW Bed Volumes (BVs) treated at the $0.7 \text{ mg}_P \text{ L}^{-1}$ breakpoint (BP), calculated as described previously [35, 36,41,42]. This BP corresponds to the future EU limit for discharge in surface water for medium-size WWTPs according to the EU Directive 2024/3019. The sorption capacity relative to each anion was assessed at the $0.7 \text{ mg}_P \text{ L}^{-1}$ BP as described in Text S2, Supplementary Material. Anion desorption and sorbent bed regeneration were performed eluting 20 BVs of a NaOH 0.5 M solution at a 10 min EBCT. For each desorption test, the overall P recovery yield was evaluated as (P mass desorbed) / (P mass fed to the adsorption test). Details relatively to the pyroaurite packing procedure, fluid-dynamic tests, BT and desorption tests are reported in Maggetti et al. [15].

3. Model

Experimental data were simulated using Aspen Adsorption, selecting the Ion Exchange equilibrium model and the axial dispersion model for the liquid phase, with mass transfer to the solid phase, as illustrated in this section.

3.1. Ion exchange equilibrium model

Preliminary simulation attempts with the different models available in Aspen Adsorption v. 14 rapidly indicated that the Ion Exchange model, combined with the Fluid-State Film option, is the most suitable one to simulate the multicomponent removal of anions with pyroaurite. Since only OH^- was tested as counterion in this work, the counterion generically indicated as c in the Aspen Adsorption guide is indicated as

OH^- in this work. The generic anion exchange reaction can therefore be represented as:

where i indicates the generic anion exchanged, m_i the valence of anion i , and S the sorbent active site. The resulting isotherm equilibrium equation is:

$$K_{i,\text{OH}} = \left(\frac{x_{i,\text{eq}}}{y_{i,\text{eq}}} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{y_{\text{OH},\text{eq}}}{x_{\text{OH},\text{eq}}} \right)^{m_i} \cdot \left(\frac{c_0}{\text{AEC}} \right)^{m_i-1} \quad (1)$$

where $K_{i,\text{OH}}$ indicates the equilibrium constant of the $i\text{-OH}$ exchange reaction ($-$), AEC the total Anion Exchange Capacity (eq m^{-3} dry sorbent), c_0 the sum of the liquid phase concentration of all anions in the inlet stream (eq m^{-3}), $x_{i,\text{eq}}$ and $x_{\text{OH},\text{eq}}$ the equilibrium molar fractions in the adsorbed phase with respect to AEC , $y_{i,\text{eq}}$ and $y_{\text{OH},\text{eq}}$ the equilibrium mole fractions in the liquid phase with respect to c_0 .

The valence m_i of each exchanged anion represents a key model parameter. For chloride and nitrate m_i is 1, while for sulfate, given the wastewater pH equal to 7.9, a valence of 2 was assumed. For carbonates, bicarbonate is the dominant species at pH 7.9, thus a valence of 1 was assumed. For phosphate, HPO_4^{2-} largely dominates over H_2PO_4^- and PO_4^{3-} at pH 7.9, even though the actual phosphate form also depends on the sorbent's properties and on the nature of the ion-exchange active sites. Previous studies conducted with a sorbent featuring iron-based adsorption sites confirm that HPO_4^{2-} is the species most likely to be exchanged at pH 7.5–8 [17]. Therefore, a valence of 2 was assumed for phosphate.

3.2. Aspen Adsorption fluid dynamic and mass transfer model

The simple plant flowsheet reported in Fig. S1 of the Supplementary Material, consisting of the inlet stream, the column and the outlet stream, was set in Aspen Adsorption to simulate the adsorption tests. The Upwind Differencing Scheme 1 (UDS 1) method was chosen for the column numerical simulation. This scheme, based upon the first-order Taylor series expansion, was selected because of its unconditionally non-oscillatory, stable nature, featuring minimum simulation time and high accuracy. On the basis of preliminary simulations, the number of nodes was set to 20.

The axial dispersion model for the liquid phase, with mass transfer to the solid phase, was selected as the fluid-dynamic model. The liquid phase local mass balance for each exchanged anion i is thus:

$$\varepsilon_{ip} \bullet \frac{\partial c_i}{\partial t} = -v_s \bullet \frac{\partial c_i}{\partial z} + \varepsilon_{ip} \bullet D_e \bullet \frac{\partial^2 c_i}{\partial z^2} - J_i'' \quad (2)$$

where z indicates the axial coordinate (m), t the time (s), c_i the liquid-phase concentration of anion i ($\text{eq m}_{\text{liquid phase}}^{-3}$), ε_{ip} the inter-particle void fraction defined as (inter-particle volume occupied by the liquid) / (total bed volume), D_e the axial dispersion coefficient ($\text{m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$), v_s the liquid superficial velocity (m/s), J_i'' the mass transfer rate between the liquid and the sorbent per volume unit of column ($\text{eq s}^{-1} \text{ m}_{\text{bed volume}}^{-3}$), considered positive if flowing towards the sorbent and defined as $J_i'' = (1 - \varepsilon_{ip}) \bullet \partial w_i / \partial t$, where w_i represents the sorbed concentration of anion i in the resin (eq m^{-3} of solid phase).

The volumetric mass transfer rate J_i'' was calculated as a function of the liquid-phase driving force:

$$J_i'' = \text{MTC}_i \bullet (c_i - c_i^{\text{eq}}) \quad (3)$$

where MTC_i is the volumetric mass transfer coefficient relative to anion i referred to the total bed volume. c_i^{eq} , the concentration of i that would be in equilibrium with the local sorbed concentration w_i , is calculated from $y_{i,\text{eq}}$, according to the ion-exchange model described by Eq. (1).

The inter-particle voidage, ε_{ip} , was assumed equal to $0.36 \text{ m}_{\text{void mbed}}^{-3}$

volume⁻³, according to Kunii and Levenspiel [43]. Based on fluid dynamics tests carried out before and after the adsorption tests as described previously [15], the total voidage ε_{tot} resulted equal to 0.63. The intra-particle voidage ε_p , determined as $(\varepsilon_{tot} - \varepsilon_{ip})/(1 - \varepsilon_{ip})$, resulted equal to 0.42.

The longitudinal dispersion coefficient D_e is assessed by Aspen Adsorption as:

$$D_e = \frac{v_{int} \cdot d_p}{0.2 + 0.11 \cdot (Re/\varepsilon_{ip})^{0.48}} \quad (4)$$

where v_{int} indicates the interstitial velocity, d_p the average particle diameter equal to 0.53 mm and Re the Reynolds number, equal to $\rho_L \cdot v_{sup} \cdot d_p / \mu_L$, where ρ_L indicates the liquid density and μ_L its viscosity.

Since the total charge of both liquid and solid phases must remain neutral, the number of counterions (OH^-) released from the sorbent and entering the liquid phase is determined as the sum of the number of all anions exchanged from the liquid phase. Therefore, J''_{OH} , the volumetric mass transfer rate of the counterion between the sorbent and the bulk liquid (eq s⁻¹ m_{bed}⁻³ volume) was calculated as:

$$J''_{OH} = - \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} J''_i \quad (5)$$

where N_c indicates the total number of anions exchanged by the column. Hence the local material balance of the exchanged counterion is the following:

$$\varepsilon_{ip} \cdot \frac{\partial c_{OH}}{\partial t} = -v_s \cdot \frac{\partial c_{OH}}{\partial z} + \varepsilon_{ip} \cdot D_e \cdot \frac{\partial^2 c_{OH}}{\partial z^2} + \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} J''_i \quad (6)$$

where c_{OH} indicates the counterion liquid-phase concentration.

3.3. Model calibration procedure

Phosphate, chloride, sulphate and nitrate were monitored during both the adsorption and desorption tests. Bicarbonate could not be measured, as the ion chromatographic method utilized a carbonate/bicarbonate mobile phase. However, given the relevant bicarbonate concentration of the tested WWTP effluent (Table 1), it was necessary to include bicarbonate in the Aspen simulation, even in the absence of a comparison with the experimental data. The potential impact of the lack of an experimental-based validation of the bicarbonate simulation is discussed in section 4.1.2. As for nitrate, given its low concentration (1.5 mg_N L⁻¹), it was decided not to include it in the Aspen simulations, considering the high measurement relative error (30–40%) and its very low impact on the overall ion exchange process (0.6% of the total inlet anion concentration expressed in equivalents).

As illustrated in section 4.1.2, ε_{ip} , ε_p , ε_{tot} and AEC were considered input parameters, constant in all simulations. The remaining parameters to be optimized were therefore the equilibrium constants $K_{PO_4,OH}$, $K_{Cl,OH}$, $K_{SO_4,OH}$, $K_{HCO_3,OH}$ and the mass transfer coefficients MTC_{PO_4} , MTC_{Cl} , MTC_{SO_4} , MTC_{HCO_3} .

These model parameters were estimated by non-linear least squares regression of the calculated anion liquid-phase concentrations to the corresponding experimental values in the breakthrough curves. The objective function to be minimized (OF) was defined as the sum of the squared deviations for the 3 measured anions (phosphate, chloride and sulfate), weighted by the squared average concentration of each anion in the feed:

$$OF = \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} \left(\frac{\sum_{j=1}^N (c_{ij}^{exp} - c_{ij}^{calc})^2}{c_{i,feed}^2} \right) \quad (7)$$

where N_c indicates the number of measured anions (3), N the number of experimental measurements for each anion in each BT curve, c_{ij}^{exp} the j^{th} measured concentration of anion i in the column outlet, c_{ij}^{calc} the corresponding calculated value and $c_{i,feed}$ the concentration of anion i in the feed.

The parameter estimation was initially performed using the experimental data of the first adsorption test (BT-a), shown in Fig. 1. In agreement with previous implementations of Aspen Adsorption to ion exchange [31], a single average MTC for all the anions - indicated in the following as \overline{MTC} - was used in the simulation. This allowed to reduce the number of parameters to be estimated from 8 to 5, and to eliminate convergence difficulties observed in preliminary attempts to estimate the complete 8-parameter vector. Unfortunately, it is not possible in Aspen Adsorption to force the use of a single MTC for all anions. Therefore, the following hybrid parameter estimation procedure was adopted, as described in more detail in section 4.1.2:

- preliminary assessment of the 4 equilibrium constants $K_{i,OH}$ using the Aspen estimator, with a constant first-guess value of \overline{MTC} equal to 0.10 s⁻¹; this value is the average of the 0.01–0.2 s⁻¹ range suggested by the demonstration cases proposed by the Aspen Adsorption Help guide for compounds with different chemical structures;
- assessment of the optimal \overline{MTC} using the estimation approach illustrated in section 3.1, maintaining the values of the 4 $K_{i,OH}$ obtained in step a);
- final assessment of the 4 equilibrium constants $K_{i,OH}$ using the Aspen estimator, maintaining the constant value of \overline{MTC} obtained in step b).

This procedure led to the identification of the best-fit parameter vector ($K_{PO_4,OH}$, $K_{Cl,OH}$, $K_{SO_4,OH}$, $K_{HCO_3,OH}$, \overline{MTC}) for adsorption test BT-a (Fig. 1). Further parameter estimations were conducted in order to obtain a parameter vector representative of all the 4 adsorption tests conducted in the 20-cm column, as illustrated in section 4.1.3. For the BT-a desorption test and the scale-up to a 60-cm column, simulations were performed only in predictive mode.

The correlation coefficient R_i^2 , defined according to Eq. (8), was used as quality indicator for the simulation of the adsorption curve of anion i :

$$R_i^2 = 1 - \left(\frac{\sum_{j=1}^N (c_{ij}^{exp} - c_{ij}^{calc})^2}{N - P - 1} \right) / \left(\frac{\sum_{j=1}^N (c_{ij}^{exp} - c_i^{mean})^2}{N - 1} \right) \quad (8)$$

where c_{ij}^{exp} indicates the j^{th} measured concentration of anion i in the column outlet, c_{ij}^{calc} the corresponding calculated value, c_i^{mean} is the mean value of the experimental c_{ij}^{exp} , N the number of experimental data and P the number of model parameters estimated in each simulation.

4. Results

4.1. Simulation of the 20-cm bed lab-scale adsorption/desorption tests

The pyroaurite P adsorption performance was investigated by means of a 3-step approach consisting of: i) isotherm and kinetic tests conducted in batch mode, ii) 4 repeated adsorption/regeneration cycles conducted in a lab-scale 20-cm packed column, and iii) 1 adsorption test conducted in a 60-cm packed column. Adsorption was conducted at a 5-min EBCT, whereas desorption was operated at a 10-min EBCT. This section focuses on the batch tests and on the 4 cycles operated in the 20-cm column.

4.1.1. Isotherm and kinetic test

A complete isotherm in the 2–40 mg_P L⁻¹ initial concentration range was conducted with the WWTP effluent described in Table 1, to assess

Fig. 1. Experimental and best-fitting simulated anion concentrations in the adsorption phase of test BT-a, conducted in the 20-cm packed bed. Concentrations are normalized by the average feed concentrations: phosphate 7 mg P L^{-1} , chloride 150 mg L^{-1} , sulphate 104 mg L^{-1} , bicarbonate 615 mg L^{-1} .

the P sorption performances of pyroaurite under equilibrium conditions [15]. As shown in Fig. S2, Supplementary Material, pyroaurite resulted in promising performances, with a maximum P sorption capacity of $26 \pm 2 \text{ mg P g}^{-1}$ in the presence of competition from other anions.

Furthermore, a 4-h kinetic test was conducted at a 30 mg P L^{-1} initial concentration, using pyroaurite granules sieved in the same size range used for the continuous tests (0.355–0.710 mm). The experimental data, shown in Fig. S3, Supplementary Material, were interpolated using the pseudo first-order, pseudo second-order and Weber Morris models, as illustrated in Text S1, Supplementary Material. The Weber Morris model resulted the best-fitting one. The results indicate that both external film mass transfer and intra-particle diffusion represent rate-limiting steps in the P sorption process, and that the 5-min EBCT selected for the continuous-flow tests represents a reasonable choice.

4.1.2. Identification of the optimal parameter vector for the adsorption step of test BT-a

The Aspen Adsorption simulation was initially based on the adsorption phase of the first BT test (BT-a), following the three steps illustrated in section 3.3. The adsorption curves of BT-a, illustrated in Fig. 1, show that chloride and sulphate were released after 190 and 240 BVs, respectively, indicating the higher affinity of pyroaurite for sulphate in comparison to chloride. Conversely, phosphate started to be slowly released after 440 BVs, as a result of the very high selectivity of pyroaurite towards this anion.

Due to competitive adsorption phenomena with phosphate, the breakthrough curves of sulphate and chloride display a noticeable peak in which the outlet-to-inlet concentration ratio ($C_{L,\text{outlet}} / C_{L,\text{inlet}}$) temporarily exceeds unity. This behaviour can be explained by the stronger affinity of pyroaurite for phosphate compared with sulphate and chloride ions. As phosphate enters the column, it preferentially occupies the adsorption sites of pyroaurite, displacing a portion of the sulphate and chloride ions that had previously been retained on the material. The anions released from the adsorbent combine with those simultaneously entering the column with the influent solution. Consequently, the measured outlet concentrations of sulphate and chloride become higher than their inlet concentrations, particularly within the range of 150 to 400 BVs. This phenomenon can impact the feasibility of reusing the treated wastewater for irrigation. Indeed, according to the FAO guidelines for agricultural reuse of treated wastewater, chloride concentrations in the $142\text{--}355 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ range require slight-to-moderate restrictions on water reuse, whereas chloride levels $>355 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ impose

severe restrictions. Considering that the MWW tested in this work presents an average chloride concentration of 150 mg L^{-1} , and that a peak in chloride outlet concentration equal to 2.3 times the inlet level is reached at 180 BVs during the P adsorption process, this phenomenon can periodically determine the occurrence of chloride outlet concentrations close to or higher than the 355 mg L^{-1} FAO threshold that imposes severe restrictions to treated MWW reuse. The occurrence of periods in each cycle with $C_{L,\text{outlet}} / C_{L,\text{inlet}} > 1$ determines a decrease in chloride and sulphate sorption capacity, which can be assessed according to the general approach illustrated in Text S2, Supplementary Material.

As illustrated in section 3.3, due to the high number of parameters to be estimated, the first step of the parameter estimation procedure consisted of the preliminary assessment of the 4 equilibrium constants $K_{i,\text{OH}}$ using the Aspen estimator, with a constant first-guess value of \overline{MTC} equal to 0.10 s^{-1} (average value of the range suggested by the Aspen Adsorption Help guide). Starting from first-guess values assigned on the basis of initial simulations, the Aspen estimator led to the identification of the following preliminary parameter vector: $K_{\text{Cl,OH}} = 1.61 \pm 0.06$, $K_{\text{SO}_4,\text{OH}} = 0.091 \pm 0.008$, $K_{\text{HCO}_3,\text{OH}} = 7.1 \pm 0.3$, $K_{\text{PO}_4,\text{OH}} = 0.88 \pm 0.18$.

The second step consisted of the assessment of the optimal average mass transfer coefficient \overline{MTC} , maintaining the above-reported values of the $K_{i,\text{OH}}$ constants. Twenty simulations of test BT-a were performed, covering the $0.01\text{--}0.15 \text{ s}^{-1}$ range suggested by the Aspen guide with a 0.01 step. The \overline{MTC} that led to the minimization of the weighted objective function (Eq. 7) resulted equal to 0.07 s^{-1} . The same 20 simulations were used to assess the model sensitivity to variations of the single \overline{MTC} (Fig. S4, Supplementary Material). Varying \overline{MTC} by $\pm 15\%$ resulted in negligible variations in the objective function (+1% when decreasing \overline{MTC} to 0.0595 s^{-1} , +5% when increasing it to 0.0805 s^{-1}). Similarly, $\pm 30\%$ variations in \overline{MTC} yielded relatively small changes in the objective function (+3% when decreasing \overline{MTC} to 0.049 s^{-1} , +9% when increasing it to 0.091 s^{-1}).

The third step consisted of the final assessment of the 4 equilibrium constants $K_{i,\text{OH}}$ using the Aspen estimator, maintaining the constant value of $\overline{MTC} = 0.07 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The best-fit simulated adsorption curves are shown in Fig. 1, whereas the optimized parameter values and the corresponding standard errors are reported in Table 2. The correlation coefficients varied between 0.94 (phosphate) and 0.99 (sulphate), indicating the effectiveness of Aspen Adsorption in simulating multi-component ion exchange phosphate removal processes, as well as the efficacy of the proposed parameter estimation procedure in overcoming

Table 2

Optimized values of the Aspen Adsorption model parameters relative to the test BT-a conducted in the 20-cm lab-scale packed bed.

Parameter	Minimized objective function (OF)	Value	Standard error
\overline{MTC}_{BT-a} (s^{-1})	Weighted average of the OFs relative to	0.07	0.01
$K_{Cl,OH-BT-a}$ (-)	Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} (Eq. (7))	2.0	0.1
$K_{HCO_3,OH-BT-a}$ (-)		9.3	0.5
$K_{SO_4,OH-BT-a}$ (-)		0.16	0.02
$K_{PO_4,OH-BT-a}$ (-)		1.6	0.2

the convergence difficulties initially encountered.

The observation of the estimated equilibrium constants confirms the higher selectivity of pyroaurite for phosphate in comparison to sulphate ($K_{PO_4,OH} / K_{SO_4,OH} = 10$) and for bicarbonate in comparison to chloride ($K_{HCO_3,OH} / K_{Cl,OH} = 4.7$), in agreement with the observation of Fig. 1. A direct comparison between the constants relative of anions with different valence is more complex. Indeed, according to the ion exchange model (Eq. (1)), the ratio between the equilibrium constants of anions with different valence depends not only on the ratio between the sorbed and liquid-phase concentrations of each anion, but also on the factor $\left(\frac{Y_{OH,eq}}{X_{OH,eq}}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{c_0}{AEC}\right)$. A comparison between the best estimates of \overline{MTC} and $K_{i,OH}$ obtained in this work and the typical literature values is reported in the Discussion section.

The dispersion coefficient resulted equal to $5.7 \cdot 10^{-5} m^2 s^{-1}$, in good agreement with the results of preliminary fluid-dynamic tests [15]. The resulting Peclet number was equal to about 7, indicating an intermediate regime in which both dispersion and convection are relevant. This result confirms the importance of using a model that includes longitudinal dispersion, an aspect neglected by numerous studies of P adsorption simulation [15] [19] [20] [21].

Further simulations were aimed at assessing how the absence of bicarbonate validation data could affect the reliability of the anion competition effects. Since the 95% confidence interval of the inlet bicarbonate concentration is equal to almost 10% of the average value ($615 \pm 58 mg L^{-1}$), in 2 additional simulations, a $\pm 10\%$ variation of the inlet bicarbonate concentration was applied. The resulting outlet concentration curves for all anions are shown in Fig. S5, Supplementary Material. A 10% decrease in inlet bicarbonate determined an 11% increase in the number of treated BVs at the 10% dimensionless phosphate breakpoint, whereas a 10% bicarbonate increase led to a 13% decrease in the number of treated BVs at the 10% P BP. This outcome indicates that the process simulation is not particularly sensitive to the variations in bicarbonate concentration that could have occurred among the different experimental tests. Two further simulations were aimed at assessing the impact of a $\pm 10\%$ variation of the best-fitting value of the bicarbonate equilibrium constant $K_{HCO_3,OH}$, equal to 9.3. As shown in Fig. S6, Supplementary Material, the $\pm 10\%$ variation of $K_{HCO_3,OH}$ had a relatively small impact on the process simulation, resulting in a $\pm 10\%$ variation in the number of treated BVs at the 10% dimensionless phosphate breakpoint (Eq. 7).

4.1.3. Simulation of four repeated 20-cm packed bed adsorption tests

An additional calibration step was performed to study the model's capacity to simulate four repeated adsorption tests conducted in the 20-cm lab-scale packed bed in the presence of minor variations in inlet P concentration, ranging from 6.5 to 7.5 $mg_P L^{-1}$. A best-fit value for the equilibrium constant $K_{PO_4,OH}$ was determined by the Aspen Adsorption estimator for each phosphate curve, using the sum of the squared deviations of the phosphorus BT curve as the objective function. All other parameters were maintained equal to those previously estimated

(Table 2). As shown in Fig. 2, this simulation strategy, limited to the adsorption steps, led to satisfactory simulations of the repeated breakthrough curves, with correlation coefficients in the 0.94–0.99 range. The estimated $K_{PO_4,OH}$ values, reported in Table 3, resulted fairly reproducible, and the best-fit values relative to the single BT curves are not significantly different from the mean $K_{PO_4,OH}$ value, equal to 1.8 ± 0.3 . Fig. 2, in agreement with the $K_{PO_4,OH}$ values reported in Table 2. This outcome indicates that the experimental and analytical errors, combined with minor variations in wastewater composition among the tests, lead to small but not negligible variations between the repeated tests, without any clear temporal trend. This suggests that a model-based approach, combined to the use of the Aspen Adsorption Cycle Organizer to simulate repeated adsorption and desorption tests, needs to be implemented to assess the long-term trend of the process performance, as will be illustrated in section 4.3.

4.1.4. Simulation of the desorption step

The main objective of the desorption step simulation is to estimate the long-term process phosphate removal/recovery performances during repeated adsorption/desorption cycles, after model calibration on a limited number of cycles conducted experimentally, previously illustrated. Aspen Adsorption was used to simulate the desorption step of BT-a in fully predictive mode, maintaining the same fluid-dynamic model, input parameters and estimated parameters of the previous adsorption step. Aspen automatically uses the final space profiles of liquid-phase and sorbed-phase concentrations in the column at the end of the adsorption phase as the initial profiles in the desorption phase. The only parameters to be set for desorption are the volumetric flow rate (50% of the adsorption flow rate, as the EBCT was doubled), and the concentration of the regenerant solution (0.5 M NaOH in water). The results, shown in Fig. 3a, indicate that the Aspen Adsorption model allowed developing a satisfactory predictive simulation of the phosphate desorption curve, with an R^2 relative to the descending portion of the curve equal to 0.96.

Since desorption was experimentally conducted in equi-current (EC) mode with respect to the previous adsorption step (that is, from the column top to the bottom), the simulation was performed in EC. As Aspen Adsorption allows to choose between equi-current and counter-current (CC) desorption, a further simulation was conducted in CC mode, with the same parameters used for the EC simulation, in order to detect possible advantages of a CC regeneration procedure. As shown in Fig. 3b, minimum differences were detected between the EC and CC simulations, indicating that there is no specific advantage in performing a counter-current desorption in the case of phosphate recovery with pyroaurite.

Fig. 2. Experimental and best-fitting simulated phosphate concentrations in the repeated adsorption tests conducted in the 20-cm bed. Concentrations are normalized by the average feed concentration of phosphate, equal to 7 $mg_P L^{-1}$.

Table 3

Optimized values of the phosphate equilibrium constant relative to the 4 repeated tests conducted in the 20-cm lab-scale packed bed. The other model parameters were maintained at constant values equal to those reported in Table 2.

Parameter	Minimized objective function (OF)	Value	Standard error
$K_{PO_4,OH-BT-a}$ (-)	OF relative only to PO_4^{3-}	1.59	0.01
$K_{PO_4,OH-BT-b}$ (-)		2.04	0.02
$K_{PO_4,OH-BT-c}$ (-)		1.97	0.01
$K_{PO_4,OH-BT-d}$ (-)		1.48	0.02

Fig. 3. (a) Experimental and simulated equi-current desorption curve relative to phosphate, after adsorption test BT-a. (b) Simulated desorption curves relative to chloride, sulphate, phosphate, and bicarbonate: comparison between the equi-current (EC) and counter-current (CC) configurations. The same parameters obtained in the optimization of the lab-scale adsorption BT tests (Tables 2 and 3) were used for the desorption simulations.

4.2. Simulation of the 60-cm bed pilot-scale adsorption test

The pyroaurite P adsorption performance was further investigated by means of an adsorption test conducted in a pilot-scale 60-cm packed column fed with the WWTP effluent described in Table 1. The scale-up was conducted at constant EBCT (5 min), which led to a 3-fold increase in superficial velocity (from 2.4 to 7.2 m/h), and consequently in Peclet number (from 7 to 21). The Aspen Adsorption simulation of the 60-cm test was conducted in predictive mode, maintaining all the parameters estimated from the 20-cm tests. As for the phosphate equilibrium constant $K_{PO_4,OH}$, the average value derived from the best fits of the 4 repeated lab-scale tests was used (1.8).

As the \overline{MTC} depends on fluid velocity, the correlations developed by Wilson and Geankoplis [44] and Kataoka et al. [45], reported in Eq. (9) and (10) respectively, were used to assess the \overline{MTC} variation resulting from the 3-fold velocity increase:

$$Sh = \frac{1.09}{\epsilon_{tot}} \cdot Re_p^{0.33} \cdot Sc^{0.33}, \quad \text{valid for } 0.0015 < Re_p < 55 \quad (9)$$

$$Sh = 1.85 \cdot \left(\frac{1 - \epsilon_{tot}}{\epsilon_{tot}} \right)^{0.33} \cdot Re_p^{0.33} \cdot Sc^{0.33}, \quad \text{valid for } Re_p < 40 \quad (10)$$

where Sh is Sherwood number = $(\overline{MTC} \cdot d_p)/D_{mol}$, Re_p the particle Reynolds number = $(v_s \cdot \rho \cdot d_p)/\mu$, and Sc the Schmidt number = $\mu/(\rho \cdot D_e)$.

Since Re_p was equal to 0.04 and 2.2 in the lab-scale and pilot-scale tests respectively, both correlations can be applied to the scale-up object of this section. Since superficial velocity is the only parameter affected by the scale-up, in this specific case both correlations can be simplified as follows:

$$\overline{MTC}_{60\text{ cm}} = \overline{MTC}_{20\text{ cm}} \cdot \left(\frac{Re_{p,60\text{ cm}}^{0.33}}{Re_{p,20\text{ cm}}^{0.33}} \right) = \overline{MTC}_{20\text{ cm}} \cdot \left(\frac{v_{s,60\text{ cm}}^{0.33}}{v_{s,20\text{ cm}}^{0.33}} \right) \quad (11)$$

The resulting $\overline{MTC}_{60\text{ cm}}$ is equal to 0.10 s^{-1} .

The experimental and simulated adsorption curves relative to the 60-cm pilot-scale test are shown in Fig. 4, together with those relative to the 20-cm test BT-a, for comparison. Fig. 4 shows that the scale-up conducted at constant EBCT was successful, as it leads to a slight shift of the BT curve to the right, indicating a small improvement in process performance. In particular, the bed volumes (BVs) corresponding to the 0.7 mg L^{-1} breakpoint (future discharge limit for medium-size WWTPs imposed by the EU Directive 2024/3019) increased from 580 (20-cm test) to 675 (60-cm test). The predictive simulation of the 60-cm test resulted in a satisfactory interpolation of the experimental data ($R^2 = 0.90$). Fig. 4 shows that the model predicts slightly higher P outlet concentrations (corresponding to lower sorbed concentrations) during the very first part of the BT curve. However, this deviation leads to a conservative assessment of the P removal performances, and it does not affect the evaluation of the treated bed volumes at the breakpoints indicated by the current and future EU legislation, which vary in the $0.5\text{--}2\text{ mg P L}^{-1}$. Overall, these results indicate that the developed Aspen Adsorption model, combined with the use of Eq. (11) to account for variations in superficial velocity, represents a reliable tool to scale up the lab-scale process of P adsorption from wastewater.

4.3. Simulation of repeated pilot-scale adsorption/desorption cycles

In order to assess the long-term process behaviour during repeated adsorption/regeneration cycles, the performance of the pyroaurite packed bed during the simulation of 5 consecutive cycles was evaluated by means of Aspen Adsorption. Each adsorption step had a constant duration (48.0 h), equal to the value required to maintain the effluent concentration at the end of each adsorption $\leq 0.7\text{ mg P L}^{-1}$ in the initial 4 cycles, and $= 0.7\text{ mg P L}^{-1}$ (10% dimensionless concentration) in the last cycle. Each desorption step had a constant duration (1.94 h), equal to the value required to achieve a P desorption yield (P mass desorbed / P mass adsorbed) equal to about 95% in the 1st desorption, and slightly lower in the subsequent ones. The simulation was conducted by means of the Aspen Adsorption Cycle Organizer, which uses the sorbed concentration profiles obtained at the end of each adsorption or desorption step as the initial condition for the next desorption or adsorption step. The first 4 of these simulated cycles correspond to the 4 repeated cycles conducted in the 20-cm packed bed, illustrated in section 4.1.3 and in Fig. 2. The simulation was thus performed for the 20-cm column, so as to allow an experimental validation of the results provided by the Cycle Organizer.

The results are illustrated in Fig. 5 in terms of simulated longitudinal profiles of P solid phase concentrations at the end of each adsorption (48 h) and desorption (1.94 h) step. Furthermore, in Fig. S7 in Supplementary Material, the dimensionless liquid-phase concentrations relative to the first four simulated adsorption steps are compared to the corresponding experimental data relative to BT-a, BT-b, BT-c, and BT-d. Fig. 5, Fig. S7, and the related data elaboration indicate that a 34% increase in final P concentration at the column outlet occurs from the 1st

Fig. 4. Experimental and best-fitting simulated phosphate concentrations in the adsorption phases of test BT-a (20-cm packed bed) and BT-pilot (60-cm packed bed). Concentrations are normalized by the average feed concentration of phosphate, equal to $7 \text{ mg}_P \text{ L}^{-1}$.

Fig. 5. Predictive simulation of the longitudinal profiles of P solid phase concentrations obtained at the end of each adsorption and each desorption step during 5 consecutive adsorption/desorption cycles in the lab-scale plant, with adsorption breakpoint $\leq 0.7 \text{ mg}_P \text{ L}^{-1}$ and P desorption yield = 95.2% in the first cycle.

to the 2nd adsorption step, due to the residual sorbed P at the end of the 1st desorption. Conversely, the increase in outlet P concentration during the subsequent adsorption steps rapidly decreases, with just a 0.07% variation between the 4th and 5th cycle. Similarly, the desorption yield obtained at constant desorption time (1.94 h), equal to 95.2% in the 1st cycle, featured a 0.8% decrease from the 1st to the 2nd step, followed by a rapid stabilization of the process, with just a 0.01% decrease in desorption yield between the 4th and 5th cycle. Furthermore, as shown in Fig. S7, the relative deviation between each simulated curve and the corresponding experimental curve varied between -1% and -7% , in terms of treated BVs at the $0.7 \text{ mg}_P \text{ L}^{-1}$. This result represents an important validation of the simulated adsorption/desorption cycles. Fig. S7 also shows that the simulated curves are always anticipated with respect to the corresponding experimental data, indicating that the Cycle Organizer provides a conservative estimate of the P sorption performances during repeated adsorption/desorption cycles.

In agreement with the experimental data shown in Fig. 2, these results clearly indicate that the pyroaurite sorption bed rapidly reaches a pseudo-stationary condition. This represents an essential requisite for the operation of a high number of consecutive adsorption/regeneration cycles at constant duration for both the sorption and desorption steps.

This analysis also shows that the Aspen Adsorption Cycle Organizer represents an effective tool to estimate the duration of each step on the basis of the selected limit for effluent discharge ($0.7 \text{ mg}_P \text{ L}^{-1}$ in this simulation). This outcome represents a crucial element for the design and cost analysis of a full-scale process.

4.4. Simulation of phosphate adsorption from saline wastewater

A further application of the model addressed the assessment of the process behaviour and performance in the presence of wastewaters affected by different levels of seawater intrusion, an increasingly common situation as a result of climate change. In a first set of simulations, chloride concentrations were increased in comparison to the average level of the tested WWTP effluent ($0.15 \text{ g}_{Cl} \text{ L}^{-1}$, Table 1), while maintaining unchanged levels for all other ions. Considering that $0.20 \text{ g}_{Cl} \text{ L}^{-1}$ is considered the threshold for seawater intrusion, and that chloride concentrations in the $0.30\text{--}0.45 \text{ g}_{Cl} \text{ L}^{-1}$ are frequently found in coastal aquifers [46], two simulations were conducted at $0.30 \text{ g}_{Cl} \text{ L}^{-1}$ (2-fold increase) and $0.45 \text{ g}_{Cl} \text{ L}^{-1}$ (3-fold increase), to mimic MWs featuring low-to-moderate degrees of salinization. Since sea water rise is expected to lead to significant increases in coastal aquifer salinization with chloride levels that could reach $1\text{--}2 \text{ g}_{Cl} \text{ L}^{-1}$ in the Mediterranean region [47] [48], two further simulations were conducted at $1 \text{ g}_{Cl} \text{ L}^{-1}$ and $2 \text{ g}_{Cl} \text{ L}^{-1}$, to take into account future climate change effects. In 2 additional simulations, considering the higher affinity of pyroaurite for sulphate in comparison to chloride (Fig. 1), the impact of increasing sulphate concentration on P removal performance was investigated, while keeping constant concentrations of the other anions. Assuming future chloride levels of 1 and $2 \text{ g}_{Cl} \text{ L}^{-1}$ in coastal aquifers, and considering that the sulphate/chloride ratio in seawater is equal to 0.14, the selected sulphate levels for these simulations were equal to $0.24 \text{ g}_{SO_4} \text{ L}^{-1}$ (baseline level equal to $0.104 \text{ g}_{SO_4} \text{ L}^{-1}$ in the experimental MWW + 14% of $1 \text{ g}_{Cl} \text{ L}^{-1}$; 35% increase from the baseline level) and $0.38 \text{ g}_{SO_4} \text{ L}^{-1}$ ($0.104 \text{ g}_{SO_4} \text{ L}^{-1}$ + 14% of $2 \text{ g}_{Cl} \text{ L}^{-1}$; 169% increase).

The results are shown in Fig. 6 in terms of P adsorption curves and in Table S1, Supplementary Material, in terms of MWW treated BVs and P sorption capacity at the 10% dimensionless breakpoint, in the benchmark condition (corresponding to Fig. 1) and in the 6 salinization scenarios.

The data elaboration indicates that, as a result of anion competition, the chloride concentrations corresponding to low-to-moderate degrees of salinization ($0.30\text{--}0.45 \text{ g}_{Cl} \text{ L}^{-1}$) determine moderate (14–25%)

Fig. 6. Simulated trends of normalized outlet phosphate concentration versus MWW treated BVs in the benchmark condition (corresponding to the anion concentrations reported in Table 1) and in different scenarios of increased chloride or sulphate concentration. The dashed line indicates the 10% dimensionless breakpoint, corresponding to $0.7 \text{ mg}_P \text{ L}^{-1}$. The treated bed volumes and the P sorption capacities evaluated at the 10% dimensionless breakpoint are reported for each scenario in Table S1, Supporting Information. Concentrations are normalized by the average feed concentration of phosphate, equal to $7 \text{ mg}_P \text{ L}^{-1}$.

decreases both in the amount of treated MWW and in the P capacity at the 10% breakpoint. Similarly, the sulphate levels corresponding to more intense salinization levels that could occur as a result of climate change ($0.24\text{--}0.38 \text{ g}_{\text{SO}_4} \text{ L}^{-1}$) lead to acceptable (17–28%) decreases in both treated BVs and P capacity. Conversely, the $1\text{--}2 \text{ g}_{\text{Cl}} \text{ L}^{-1}$ chloride concentrations that could be encountered in coastal aquifers as a result of climate change scenarios determine marked (43–67%) decreases in P adsorption performances. These results indicate that, thanks to its high selectivity for phosphate, pyroaurite can withstand moderate increases in salt concentration, whereas future marked salinization scenarios can potentially lead to relevant decreases in the P removal/recovery performances. This analysis also indicates that the Aspen Adsorption-based multicomponent adsorption/IEX model can represent a useful tool to predict the impact of MWW salinity on P removal performances.

5. Discussion

The literature analysis relative to the simulation of IEX processes indicates that this study features a relevant progress in comparison to the very limited number of studies relative to the use of Aspen Adsorption to simulate anion or cation exchange processes [31] [32] [30] [29]. Indeed, as liquid-phase desorption/regeneration was not previously simulated in Aspen, the use of the Cycle Organizer was not documented beforehand. Furthermore, the use of Aspen Adsorption to calibrate the model on experimental data of multicomponent ion exchange, which presents specific convergence challenges due to the high number of parameters to be estimated, was not documented in the previous studies, which were mostly limited to purely predictive simulations without any best-fit on experimental data and/or to single-component ion exchange [31] [30] [29].

Moving to other studies that simulated IEX processes with different types of software, Zhang and Selim [24] modelled the competitive phosphate-arsenate transport and adsorption on soils using a Crank-Nicholson explicit-implicit method solved with a 4th-order Runge-Kutta scheme, whereas Simonnot and Ouvrard [23] modelled the competitive anion exchange of sulphate, nitrate and chloride on a commercial resin using an IMPACT computer code. Both studies assumed solid/liquid equilibrium and did not include desorption in their

simulation, thus neglecting key modelling features developed in this work. On the one hand, in agreement with previous works [49], Zhang and Selim [24] found that estimating adsorption equilibrium coefficients based on preliminary batch tests leads to poor simulation of continuous-flow tests. On the other hand, several studies implemented simplified adsorption models, such as the Thomas, Yoon-Nelson, or Adams-Bohart models, which do not consider axial dispersion, mass-transfer resistances, or anion competition [15] [19] [20] [21].

Due to the limited number of studies that simulate IEX processes with mass transfer and ion competition, the comparison between the estimates of the model parameters (MTC s and equilibrium constants) obtained in this work and those reported in the literature is not straightforward. Starting from the mass-transfer coefficients, Jurado-Davila et al. [22] tested P adsorption using a layered double hydroxide as adsorbent and simulated the breakthrough curves by numerical integration of the mass balances. The best-fitting dimensionless numbers of their model correspond to phosphate MTC s in the $0.01\text{--}0.15 \text{ s}^{-1}$ range, depending on the operational condition, in good agreement with the 0.07 s^{-1} \overline{MTC} estimated in this work. Korai et al. [29] used Aspen Adsorption to simulate fluoride removal from groundwater with activated alumina, zeolite and China Clay. They used a fixed MTC of 0.5 s^{-1} for all three sorbents. Goh et al. [36] used Aspen adsorption and an artificial neural network to simulate atenolol adsorption on a gasified woodchips activated carbon. They estimated an MTC of 0.024 s^{-1} . Gallindo et al. [32], in a study of ion exchange for Zn^{2+} removal using zeolite NaY, estimated a 0.002 s^{-1} MTC referred to a solid-phase driving force. Therefore, this value cannot be directly compared to our \overline{MTC} , referred to a liquid-phase driving force. Given the very limited availability of MTC literature values relative to anions, a theoretical evaluation of the MTC_i relative to each anion simulated in this work (phosphate, chloride, bicarbonate and sulphate) was performed based on literature correlations [44] [45], with the double goal to validate the choice to use an average \overline{MTC} for all anions and to perform a literature-based assessment of our \overline{MTC} best estimate ($0.07 \pm 0.01 \text{ s}^{-1}$). Two in-series types of mass transport were considered: mass transfer from the bulk of the liquid to the outer surface of the particle (external film mass transfer), and internal mass transfer within the pores. The estimation of the external and internal mass transfer coefficients, as well as of the

overall combined MTC_i for each anion, was conducted as described in Text S3, Supplementary Material. The range of variation of the overall, internal and external MTC_i resulted equal to $0.03 - 0.09 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for phosphate, $0.07 - 0.21 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for chloride, $0.04 - 0.13 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for bicarbonate, and $0.04 - 0.14 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for sulfate. All these values are of the same order of magnitude, and an overlap zone ($0.07\text{--}0.09 \text{ s}^{-1}$) exists between the estimated ranges. This outcome supports the choice of a single average \overline{MTC} for all anions. The fact that the best-fitting value obtained for the average \overline{MTC} (0.07 s^{-1}) falls within the overlap zone represents a further validation of the proposed model calibration approach.

Moving on to the equilibrium constants, the literature analysis indicates that a direct comparison between the values estimated in this work and those of other studies is not possible, due to the variety of equilibrium models adopted [50]. On the other hand, comparisons with a limited number of studies can be made in terms of the binary separation factor (or selectivity factor) $\alpha_{PO4/j}$ of the tested sorbent for phosphate in comparison to another anion j , defined at liquid-solid equilibrium as:

$$\alpha_{PO4/j} = \frac{w_{PO4}^{eq}}{c_{PO4}^{eq}} \cdot \frac{c_j^{eq}}{w_i^{eq}} \quad (12)$$

In this work the $\alpha_{PO4/j}$ selectivities - calculated from the liquid- and solid-phase concentrations estimated by Aspen in the saturation condition at the end of the simulation of BT-a - resulted equal to 25 for phosphate/chloride, 10 for phosphate/sulphate and 5.3 for phosphate/bicarbonate. Fang et al. [51] developed and tested an As(III)-ion imprinted polymer (As-IIP) and provided separation factors from which it is possible to estimate $\alpha_{PO4/j}$ values equal to 1.4, 2.1 and 1.1 for chloride, nitrate, and sulphate, respectively. Iddya et al. [52], in a study of phosphate separation using a reverse-selective ion exchange membrane, obtained selectivities equal to 20 for phosphate/chloride and 47 for phosphate/sulphate. Zhao and Sengupta [53], using a polymeric ligand exchanger, obtained phosphate/sulphate selectivities in the 15–20 range. Sengupta and Pandit [54] tested a hybrid anion exchanger containing Fe nanoparticles, and estimated an $\alpha_{\text{phosphate/sulphate}}$ equal to 46. These literature values are in reasonable agreement with those estimated in this work.

Lastly, the correlation coefficients (R^2) obtained through the model calibration procedure illustrated in sections 4.1.2 and 4.1.3 (0.94–0.99) are in good agreement with those reported in the literature for adsorption/IEX processes simulated with Aspen (0.992–0.998) [32], with the Thomas model (0.970–0.998) [32] or by numerical integration of the mass balances (0.94–0.99) [22]. The 0.90 R^2 obtained in section 4.2 for the scale-up to the 60-cm packed bed, even though slightly lower than the typical literature values, is still considered a satisfactory value, taking into account the purely predictive simulation approach applied in section 4.2 and the application of literature correlations to estimate the variation of \overline{MTC} with water velocity.

This literature analysis indicates that the phosphate adsorption/desorption model developed and validated in this work includes several innovative elements, each of which is of high relevance for a model-based scale-up towards real-world applications: i) the experimental validation and the simulation of the desorption step, and therefore the use of the Cycle Organizer to predict the process behaviour during repeated adsorption/desorption cycles; ii) the competitive effect exerted by other anions, a crucial feature to predict the process effectiveness in the presence of MWWs with different salinity; iii) longitudinal dispersion, a fundamental characteristic in particular for the simulation of lab-scale processes featuring low packed-bed heights and therefore low Peclet numbers (<1), indicating a fluid-dynamic condition strongly affected by dispersion; iv) a liquid/solid mass-transfer term which enables the simulation of non-equilibrium P recovery processes, a relevant feature in the frequent case of IEX processes conducted at low EBCT; and v) an innovative procedure to calibrate the model on experimental

breakthrough curves based on the use of a single average \overline{MTC} .

Future developments of the process simulation required to scale-up the process to full-scale applications include: i) the model-based optimization of the desorption phase, to reduce the bed volumes of regenerant solution and therefore the consumption of chemicals; ii) the model-based assessment of the optimal adsorption EBCT; iii) the use of the Cycle Organizer to simulate repeated adsorption/desorption cycles characterized by the reuse of the same regeneration solution; iv) the simulation of the final step of P recovery from the desorption solution by chemical precipitation and of the subsequent solid/liquid separation, to allow an optimization of precipitation agent concentration, contact time and mixing intensity; and v) the model-based scale-up of the process to full-scale conditions, to develop a process inventory and a cost-benefit analysis of the proposed P removal/recovery process, including different scenarios in terms of market price of the P-rich product and number of adsorption/desorption cycles that can be performed with the same resin load.

The proposed P adsorption/recovery model can be easily adapted to other sorbents and wastewater types, thereby broadening its future applications across diverse real-world conditions. This model adaptation can be achieved through the following steps: a) in case of a different sorbent, insert its total void fraction, inter-particle void fraction, bulk density, sorbent total capacity and average particle diameter in the “Specify” table within the “Configure Block Bed” window; b) in case of a wastewater with different salinity, insert the anion concentrations in the “Specify” table within the “Configure Stream F1” window; c) update the parameter best-fit on the experimental data following the procedure illustrated in sections 3.3 and 4.1.2 of this work.

6. Conclusions

This research innovatively utilized Aspen Adsorption to model multicomponent ion exchange for phosphate removal and recovery from wastewater. It successfully incorporated competitive effects from major anions, mass transfer limitations, and dynamic adsorption–desorption behaviour. A novel predictive model was developed and calibrated using continuous-flow tests conducted with pyroaurite, a Fe-rich hydroxalite highly selective for phosphate.

A hybrid parameter estimation method enabled the accurate calibration of both equilibrium constants and mass transfer coefficients, overcoming the typical convergence issues in multicomponent liquid-phase systems. The model reliably reproduced the breakthrough and regeneration curves for phosphate, sulphate, and chloride ($R^2 \geq 0.90$), confirming its validity across both adsorption and desorption phases. Incorporating a solid–liquid mass-transfer term and an axial dispersion model proved crucial for describing the non-equilibrium sorption characteristic at short empty-bed contact times (EBCT).

Predictive simulations accurately mirrored the scale-up from a 20-cm to a 60-cm packed bed, operated at constant EBCT. Literature correlations were used to account for changes in the mass transfer coefficient due to increased superficial velocity. The Aspen Cycle Organizer allowed for realistic simulation of repeated adsorption–desorption cycles, showing that the pyroaurite bed quickly achieved a pseudo-stationary regime with stable phosphate removal and recovery yields exceeding 95%. The model was also applied to evaluate the effect of increasing water salinity, a growing concern in the climate change era. Adsorption efficiency decreased by $\leq 25\%$ even with a threefold increase in chloride concentration. This result confirms pyroaurite's robustness for treating saline wastewaters and the utility of Aspen Adsorption for exploring process resilience under fluctuating feed compositions.

Overall, this study shows that the experimentally validated Aspen-based model of P adsorption and recovery has a strong potential for the design and optimization of a full-scale process, thanks to the possibility to i) scale up the process taking into account the MTC variation with superficial velocity, ii) optimize the adsorption and desorption

EBCT, iii) estimate the duration of the adsorption and desorption steps required to ensure long-term compliance with discharge limits, and iv) predict the competitive effect exerted by saline wastewaters. The proposed model thus promotes the transition from laboratory-scale results into sustainable, full-scale phosphorus recovery technologies, advancing circular resource management in wastewater treatment.

Abbreviations and symbols

<i>BP</i>	Breakpoint
<i>BT</i>	Breakthrough Test
<i>BVs</i>	Bed Volumes
<i>CC</i>	Counter-current
c_c	Counter ion concentration in liquid phase (eq/m ³)
c_i	Ion concentration of exchanged ion <i>i</i> in liquid phase (eq/m ³)
$c_{i,feed}$	Concentration of anion <i>i</i> in the feed (eq/m ³)
c_i^{eq}	Liquid phase concentration of ion <i>i</i> in equilibrium with resin phase (eq/m ³)
c_i^{mean}	Mean value of the experimental $c_{i,j}^{exp}$ (eq/m ³)
$c_{i,j}^{exp}$	j^{th} measured concentration of anion <i>i</i> in the column outlet (eq/m ³)
$c_{i,j}^{calc}$	j^{th} calculated concentration of anion <i>i</i> in the column outlet (eq/m ³)
c_0	Total anions concentration in liquid phase in the inlet stream (eq/m ³)
d_p	Sorbent particle diameter (m)
D_e	Axial dispersion coefficient (m ² /s)
<i>EBCT</i>	Empty Bed Contact Time
<i>EQ</i>	Equi-current
<i>IEX</i>	Ion exchange
J_c''	Counter ion material transfer rate per volume unit of column (eq m ⁻³ s ⁻¹)
J_i''	Ion <i>i</i> material transfer rate per volume unit of column (eq m ⁻³ s ⁻¹)
K_{ic}	Mass action equilibrium constant between ion <i>i</i> and the counterion <i>c</i> (–)
m_i	Stoichiometric coefficient used in mass action equilibrium (valence ratio <i>c/i</i>) (–)
<i>MWW</i>	Municipal wastewater
<i>MTC</i>	volumetric mass transfer coefficient referred to solid phase volume (1/s)
MTC_i	volumetric mass transfer coefficient relative to anion <i>i</i> referred to the total bed volume (1/s)
<i>N</i>	Number of experimental measurements
N_c	Total number of anions exchanged by the column
<i>AEC</i>	Anionic Exchange Capacity (eq/m ³) - in Aspen total ion capacity, <i>Q</i>
<i>S</i>	Sorbent active site
<i>t</i>	Time (s)
w_i	Ion <i>i</i> loading on sorbent (eq/m ³)
w_i^{eq}	Ion <i>i</i> loading in equilibrium with liquid phase ion concentration (eq/m ³)
<i>WW</i>	Wastewater
<i>WWTP</i>	Wastewater treatment plant
$x_{i,eq}$	Ion <i>i</i> equilibrium molar fractions in the adsorbed phase with respect to <i>AEC</i>
x_i	Ion <i>i</i> mole fraction in adsorbed (sorbent) phase (–)
$y_{i,eq}$	Ion <i>i</i> equilibrium mole fractions in the liquid phase with respect to c_0
y_i	Ion <i>i</i> mole fraction in liquid phase (–)
v_s	liquid superficial velocity (m/s)
v_{int}	= v_s/ϵ_{tot} , liquid interstitial velocity (m/s)
<i>z</i>	Axial coordinate (m)
$\alpha_{PO4/j}$	Selectivity of a given ion exchanger for phosphate in

	comparison to anion <i>j</i>
ϵ_{tot}	Total bed voidage (–)
ϵ_{ip}	Inter-particle voidage (–)
ϵ_p	Intra-particle voidage (pore structure) (–)
μ	Liquid viscosity (N m ⁻² s ⁻¹ - Pa • s)
ρ	Liquid density (kg/m ³)

Dimensionless numbers

<i>Sh</i>	= $(\overline{MTC} \bullet d_p)/D_{mol}$, Sherwood number D_{mol} = average diffusivity
Re_p	= $(\rho \bullet d_p \bullet v_s)/\mu$, particle Reynolds number
<i>Sc</i>	= $\mu/(\rho \bullet D_e)$, Schmidt number
<i>Pe</i>	= $Re \bullet Sc = (v_s \bullet H_B)/D_e$, Peclet number. H_B = packed bed height.

Subscripts

<i>i</i>	exchanged anion
<i>c</i>	counterion
<i>p</i>	particle (sorbent)

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Davide Pinelli: Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Benedetta Martellotti:** Software, Investigation, Data curation. **Elisa Girometti:** Software, Methodology, Investigation. **Laura Bernacchioni:** Validation, Software. **Giacomo Antonioni:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Conceptualization. **Valerio Cozzani:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Dario Frascari:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Investigation, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2026.110163>.

Data availability

Research data underlying this manuscript have been published in the Zenodo Research Repository (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17803792)

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